

The Influence of Numbered Head Together (NHT) Cooperative Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes Theme 2 Subtheme 1 "Harmony in Differences" in Class VI Students at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar

Frans Warnen Horen Saruksuk^{1*}, Lisbet Novianti Sihombing², Desi Sijabat³
Universitas HKBP Nommensen Pematangsiantar

Corresponding Author: Frans Warnen Horen Saruksuk fwhs0314@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to improve student learning outcomes in thematic learning Theme 2 Subtheme 1 through the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model. This research was carried out at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar with the research subjects being class VI with 30 students. This type of research uses an experimental method with a One Group Pretest-Posttest Design research design. Data collection techniques are tests and documentation. Data analysis techniques are descriptive statistical tests and hypothesis testing. The research results show an increase in student learning outcomes through the Numbered Head Together (NHT) cooperative learning model. This is evidenced by the increase in student completion scores, where the average pre-test score is 60.8 and the average post-test score is 83.06, so it can be concluded that the application of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) learning model has affected the results. Student learning is said to be quite effective.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the first step for someone to gain and gain insight and knowledge through the learning and teaching process distributed by teachers to students which is held in schools as formal educational institutions. that education is a form of effort made to provide knowledge and self-development through guidance activities that are inherent to a person in the teaching process distributed by teachers in formal institutions such as schools, which of course there are results obtained by students after carrying out the learning process, namely learning outcomes .

Based on the research conducted, it was still found that the learning process carried out in the classroom by teachers still carried out conventional learning. So it was found that there was still a lack of student learning outcomes, especially in group-based learning. Students at these elementary schools still have poor learning outcomes. In learning, there are still many students who are busy with themselves while learning is taking place, many are chatting with their classmates, daydreaming and not paying attention to the ongoing learning process.

Apart from that, there are still many students who feel bored while learning and feel sleepy. So, when evaluating the learning material by the teacher, many students were found who did not understand the learning material taught by the teacher. This will cause the low learning outcomes of class VI students at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

A learning model is a conceptual framework in the form of a systematic procedural pattern used to plan learning in order to achieve learning goals. A learning model is a learning approach that will be used including the learning objectives that will be used, the stages of learning activities and management in the classroom during learning, learning models are usually prepared based on various principles or theories of knowledge.

Experts develop learning models based on learning principles, psychological, sociological theories, systems analysis, or other supporting theories. The benefit of having a learning model is as a guide for teaching designers and teachers in implementing learning. The choice of learning model is greatly influenced by the nature of the material to be taught, the objectives to be achieved in the learning and the level of ability of the students. The function of the learning model is as a guide for teaching designers and teachers in implementing learning. Learning models have several types of Learning Design Models, Contextual Learning Models (Contextual Teaching and Learning, Problem Based Learning Models (PBM), Thematic Learning Models, PAKEM Models (Participatory, Active, Creative, Effective and Fun), Independent Learning Models , Lesson Study Model (Learning Approach), Cooperative Learning Model (Cooperative Learning). And in this research the learning model used is the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model.

According to Slavin (Rusman, 2010: 201), cooperative learning encourages students to interact actively and positively in groups where they can exchange ideas and examine their own ideas in a non-threatening

atmosphere, in accordance with philosophy and constructivism. Cooperative learning is useful as cooperative learning encourages students to interact actively and positively in groups who are allowed to exchange ideas and examine their own ideas in a non-threatening atmosphere, in accordance with philosophy and constructivism. Cooperative learning is useful as the use of cooperative learning can improve student learning achievement and at the same time improve social relations, foster attitudes of tolerance and respect for other people's opinions. Especially in implementing the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model. According to Slavin (Miftahul Huda, 2014: 203) this learning method was developed to ensure individual accountability in group discussions. The purpose of NHT is to provide opportunities for students to share ideas and consider the most appropriate answers for all subjects and grade levels. The Numbered Heads Together (NHT) type cooperative model is very useful for improving students' thinking power, because this learning model involves more students in studying the material covered in a lesson and checking their understanding of the content of the lesson to achieve a learning outcome value student. The steps for the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model are as follows:

- Phase 1: Numbering. The teacher divides students into groups of 3-5 people and each group member is given a number 1 to 5.
- Phase 2: Asking questions. The teacher asks a question to the students. Questions may vary. Questions can be specific and in the form of interrogative sentences.
- Phase 3: Thinking together. Students unite their opinions on the answer to the question and make sure each member of their team knows the team's answer.
- Phase 4: Answer. The teacher calls a certain number, then the student whose number matches raises his hand and tries to answer the question for the whole class.

The implementation of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model is expected to influence student learning outcomes, especially for class VI UPTD students at SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar. According to R Ibrahim (Istirani, 2016: 17) said that learning outcomes are the main components that teachers must first formulate in the teaching and learning process which are obtained through the teaching and learning process at school, one of which is expressed in numbers and measured using learning outcomes tests.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Cooperative learning is useful as cooperative learning encourages students to interact actively and positively in groups who are allowed to exchange ideas and examine their own ideas in a non-threatening atmosphere, in accordance with philosophy and constructivism. Cooperative learning is useful as the use of cooperative learning can improve student learning achievement and at the same time improve social relations, foster attitudes of tolerance and respect for other people's opinions. Especially in implementing

the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model. According to Slavin (Miftahul Huda, 2014: 203) this learning method was developed to ensure individual accountability in group discussions. The purpose of NHT is to provide opportunities for students to share ideas and consider the most appropriate answers for all subjects and grade levels.

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is experimentation with a quantitative approach. Arikunto (2018:9) states that experimentation is one of the methods used to look for a causal relationship (casual relationship) between two factors that are deliberately created by researchers by eliminating or reducing other disturbing factors. The type of research carried out was the Pre-Experimental Design method, with a research design using a One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design. The population in this research is all class VI students consisting of 30 students in one class and the sample for this research is 30 students. The instrument in this research is a test instrument. The instruments in this research are test questions which are tested using validity tests, reliability tests, difficulty level tests, and differential power tests. Other data is collected through documentation results. Then the data results were analyzed using hypothesis testing using the paired samples test analysis technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted in class VI UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar for the 2023/2024 academic year from 02 October to 14 October 2023. The population used in this research were all students in class VI UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar with a class VI research sample of 30 students. In this section, the results found in the research will be described. The intended results are conclusions drawn based on the data collected and data analysis that has been carried out.

This research aims to determine the influence of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) Cooperative Learning Model on the learning outcomes of Class VI Students in the Learning Subtheme "Harmony in Difference" at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

Based on the pre-test results, the average student learning outcome score was 60.8 with 26 students scoring below the KKM and 4 students scoring above the KKM. Looking at the existing percentage results, it can be said that the level of student learning outcomes before using the Numbered Head Together (NHT) cooperative learning model was relatively low.

Furthermore, the average score of the post-test results was 83.06, so after using the Numbered Head Together (NHT) cooperative learning model, students had better learning results than before using the Numbered Head Together (NHT) cooperative learning model, where there were 30 students in the category completed above KKM.

After carrying out the pre-test and post-test normality tests, a homogeneity test was carried out. Based on the homogeneity test, a significant value of 0.08 was obtained. Based on the criteria that have been determined: if the sig value is > 0.05 then the data is said to have homogeneous variation.

After carrying out the homogeneity test, a t test was carried out to show that the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ value was $10.275 > 2.042$ or significant $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. So it can be concluded that there is "The influence of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) Cooperative Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes Theme 2 Subtheme 1 "Harmony in Differences" in Class VI Students at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar"

The results of the analysis above which show the influence of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) cooperative learning model are in line with the results of the observations made. Based on the results of observations, there were changes in students, namely that at the beginning of learning activities students were busy with themselves during the learning process, often chatting with their classmates, often daydreaming and not paying attention to learning. However, in line with the use of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) cooperative learning model, students begin to be active in the learning process. Observation results show that students pay attention to the teacher's explanations and are serious when participating in learning and express opinions when the teacher asks questions. Students are increasingly able to work together in group discussion activities. Students also begin to be active and confident in helping friends if a friend is experiencing difficulties and asking the teacher if they do not understand.

A fun learning process makes students no longer come in and out during learning and no longer feel bored, sleepy and daydreaming or depressed when following the learning process in class so that students are motivated to take part in learning and feel happy in group discussion activities, thereby raising students' interest in learning more. Seriously following the learning process that can improve student learning outcomes.

Based on the results of descriptive statistical tests and pre-requisite test results obtained as well as the results of observations that have been made, it can be concluded that there is an influence in the use of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) type cooperative learning model on student learning outcomes for theme 2 subtheme 1 "Harmony in Differences" in class VI students at UPTD SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

Table 1. YT Test Result

Paired Samples Test								
	Paired Differences				T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper

Pa ir 1	Post Test - Pre Test	22,267	11,870	2,167	17,834	26,699	10,275	29	0.000
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Based on table 1 above, it can be concluded that Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted. This means that there is an influence of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Subtheme 1 "Harmony in Difference" in Class VI UPTD of SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research conducted by researchers in class V UPTD SDN 124385 Pematang Siantar, it can be concluded that Ho was rejected and Ha was accepted. This means that there is an influence of the Numbered Head Together (NHT) Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes in Theme 2 Subtheme 1 "Harmony in Difference" in Class VI UPTD of SD Negeri 124385 Pematang Siantar.

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